

sat-os

build

```
rustup default stable  
cargo build --release
```

sim

```
cargo run --release -- sim --orbit leo-500km-ss0 --duration 12h --seed 7
```

Artifacts: - `./out/events.ndjson` - `./out/health.bin` - `./out/trace.bin`

run (target)

```
cargo run --release -- flight --board <cfg>
```

layout

```
sat-os/  
  Cargo.toml  
  src/  
    main.rs  
    bus.rs  
    mode.rs  
    budgets.rs  
    scheduler.rs  
    faults.rs  
    trace.rs  
    log.rs  
    devices/  
      mod.rs  
      eps.rs  
      thermal.rs  
      adcs.rs  
      comms.rs  
    sim/  
      mod.rs
```

```
orbit.rs
env.rs
devices_sim.rs
configs/
boards/
missions/
tools/
ground/
  decode_trace.py
  plot_health.py
```

invariants

- No heap allocation in control loop.
- Bounded compute per tick.
- Single-writer event log.
- Mode transitions are total-order and timestamped.
- Hard limits preempt opportunity logic.

ports

Device API surface:

- `eps.*` (bus V/I, SoC, solar I, rails)
- `thermal.*` (temps, heaters, louvers)
- `adcs.*` (attitude, rates, point)
- `comms.*` (link, windows, buffer, tx/rx)

modes

```
SAFE           : min load, beacon, thermal survival
SUN_CHARGE     : charge bias, shed loads, opportunistic rx
ECLIPSE_SURVIVE : battery protect, thermal conserve
NOMINAL        : scheduled payload/tx within budgets
DOWNLINK       : point+tx, drain buffer, elevate comms budgets
PAYLOAD        : point+operate, watchdog margins
```

loop

Tick (default 1 Hz):

1) sample `eps/thermal/adcs/comms` 2) compute margins (energy/thermal/comms/control) 3) select mode (hard-bounds first) 4) derive budgets (W, duty, tx) 5) schedule tasks under budgets 6) execute actions (bounded) 7) append trace + health

thresholds (mission cfg)

```
SoC_FLOOR_SAFE=0.20
SoC_FLOOR_ECLIPSE=0.35
TEMP_MAX_SAFE_C=75.0
BUFFER_DOWNLINK_MIN=0.30
CHARGE_TARGET=0.55
```

example

`src/mode.rs`

```
#[derive(Clone, Copy, Debug, PartialEq, Eq)]
pub enum Mode { Safe, SunCharge, Nominal, EclipseSurvive, Downlink, Payload }

pub struct Margins {
    pub soc: f32,           // 0..1
    pub temp_max_c: f32,   // C
    pub eclipse: bool,
    pub downlink_open: bool,
    pub buffer_fill: f32,  // 0..1
    pub adcs_ok: bool,
}

pub fn choose_mode(m: &Margins) -> Mode {
    if !m.adcs_ok { return Mode::Safe; }
    if m.soc < 0.20 || m.temp_max_c > 75.0 { return Mode::Safe; }
    if m.eclipse && m.soc < 0.35 { return Mode::EclipseSurvive; }
    if m.downlink_open && m.buffer_fill > 0.30 { return Mode::Downlink; }
    if !m.eclipse && m.soc < 0.55 { return Mode::SunCharge; }
    Mode::Nominal
}
```

src/scheduler.rs

```
#[derive(Clone, Debug)]
pub struct Task { pub name: &'static str, pub cost_w: f32, pub prio: u8 }

pub fn schedule(mut tasks: Vec<Task>, power_budget_w: f32) -> Vec<Task> {
    tasks.sort_by_key(|t| t.prio);
    let mut out = Vec::new();
    let mut used = 0.0;
    for t in tasks {
        if used + t.cost_w <= power_budget_w {
            used += t.cost_w;
            out.push(t);
        }
    }
    out
}
```

faults

```
CLASS0 transient      : retry/vote
CLASS1 resource       : shed → charge/survive
CLASS2 control        : detumble/re-init → SAFE
CLASS3 comms/watchdog : SAFE + beacon + timed ladder
```

trace

- `events.ndjson` (human)
- `trace.bin` (binary decision trace)
- `health.bin` (telemetry frame stream)